

Welcome to the latest PQ-REACT insights #8 Edition

Dear readers,

We welcome you to our 8th PQ-REACT Newswave. An issue filled with results, progress and exciting milestones. With just a few months left before the project's end, we work tirelessly to deliver the final results and share them with communities across Europe. **But how?**

Primarily at our **joint SPQR Cluster and PQ-REACT final event in Bucharest, Romania, on the 11th of June**, where we look forward to bringing together researchers, policymakers, legal experts, and EU project representatives for a memorable closing event.

And not only! Stay tuned with PQ-REACT and dive into our Quantum world!

Explore our SPQR & PQ-REACT final event

Our Quantum world in motion

Today, our world runs on secure digital communication, from banking and smartphones to smart homes and public services. But what if tomorrow's computers could break that security super fast and effortlessly?

Quantum computers are still emerging, but they could eventually solve problems that today's digital defences rely on, like protecting passwords, messages, and even national infrastructure.

Watch the video and discover how PQ-REACT is securing the quantum future!

PQ-REACT Key Exploitable Results

What is a Key Exploitable Result in a Horizon EU project?

A **Key Exploitable Result (KER)** in a Horizon EU project is a concrete output with clear potential for real-world use and impact. It goes beyond general results or findings. KERs are the most valuable, innovation-driven outcomes

of a project that can be used, scaled, or commercialised. These may include new technologies, methodologies, datasets, policy recommendations, or prototypes.

The PQ-REACT Key Exploitable Results list **includes seven key outputs** with strong potential for real-world application, commercialisation, and further research. They include tools, frameworks, algorithms, and methodologies that smooth and secure the transition to the postquantum world.

[Explore the full list](#)

Events & Collaborations

Coming Soon

QSNS 2026

The 3rd edition of the **QSNS workshop** will be co-located with the 31st IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications, and will take place from **June 23-26, 2026, at Vilamoura, Algarve, Portugal.**

The 2026 edition is a joint initiative of the SPQR cluster projects, co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe framework programme on the transition to **Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC)** of protocols, networks, and systems.

[Learn more](#)

Beyond the Algorithm: The Road to Quantum-Safe Europe

The SPQR cluster and the PQ-REACT project are organising the **"Beyond the Algorithm: The Road to Quantum-Safe Europe"** on the 11th of June 2026 at the Nord Events Centre by Globalworth in Bucharest, Romania.

Bringing together researchers, policymakers, legal experts, and EU project representatives, the event will explore and help define the future of **post-quantum cryptography (PQC)** across Europe and beyond.

The agenda includes representation from SPQR cluster projects, with an emphasis on live demonstrations of real-world post-quantum cryptography applications, as well as the winners of the **PQ-REACT Open Call #2**, which will also take the stage to showcase their projects and findings.

Learn more & Secure your Spot today

Just Concluded

From Sea to Cyberspace: Securing Europe in the Quantum Era

The joint webinar of the [PQ-REACT](#) & [SMAUG](#) EU projects, "From Sea to Cyberspace: Securing Europe in the Quantum Era", took place on Tuesday, 5th of May 2026.

During the webinar, the cybersecurity challenges **facing critical infrastructure, including the maritime ecosystem**, were explored with a focus on quantum threats.

[Watch the full recording](#)

PQ-REACT Training Pills

In this session, we explored why crisis communication requires strategy, structure, and preparedness. **Our Open Call winners** were guided through real-world scenarios showing how a simple issue can quickly escalate into a communication crisis or, alternatively, become a communication opportunity.

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Crisis and Reputation Management

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Exploitation: A Deep Dive
on Asset Exploitation

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Exploitation: A Deep Dive on Asset
Exploitation

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Publications & Open Access

PQ-REACT has produced **21 scientific publications to date**, authored by experts across the project's consortium. Covering topics ranging from cryptographic agility and PQC migration to validation frameworks and real-world implementation, these works contribute to the growing research field on post-quantum cryptography.

Discover the PQ-REACT publications

What's next?

As PQ-REACT moves into its closing phase, our focus turns to maximising impact and visibility. We are looking forward to a busy summer, with multiple opportunities to showcase our results, especially at our final event in Bucharest! In parallel, our Open Call 2 winners will also be finalising their projects, and we look forward to seeing their results and real-world implementations come to life.

Stay tuned for more updates!

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